

Parameters affecting plug characteristics in dense phase pneumatic conveying of ellipsoidal particles

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS

- CFD-DEM study on the effect of particle shape on plug flow dense phase conveying.
- Parameters affecting the steady state plug characteristics are identified.
- Spherical vs. ellipsoidal particles: Distinct steady state plug characteristics.
- Rolling friction matches speed and length of ellipsoidal and spherical particle plugs.

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ABSTRACT

Even though particle shape tends to have a major influence on the bulk behaviour of a granular system, perfectly spherical particles are often used in numerical simulations. In this study, we examine the plug flow of ellipsoidal particles in dense phase horizontal pneumatic conveying within a rigid and cylindrical pipe with periodic boundaries in the axial direction. We use coupled Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) – Discrete Element Method (DEM) simulations to investigate the effect of particle shape on four plug characteristics: velocity, length, porosity, and particle exchange rate with the stationary bed. Both ellipsoidal and spherical particles are used, and the parameters varied are the particle size, aspect ratio, pressure gradient, particle–particle and particle–wall sliding and rolling friction coefficients, and coefficients of restitution. The steady state characteristics of plugs composed of spherical particles are distinctly different from those composed of ellipsoidal particles. Certain parameters, including the particle–wall rolling friction and restitution coefficients, have minimal impact on the steady state plug characteristics. The present study also suggests that introducing interparticle rolling friction for perfectly spherical particles can achieve the velocity and length appropriate for plugs composed of ellipsoidal particles, although differences in dynamics may persist. Overall, this comprehensive analysis offers valuable insights into plug flow behaviour with non-spherical particles, aiding in the efficient modelling and design of pneumatic conveying systems.

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1. Introduction

Pneumatic conveying is widely used for the transport of granular materials in various industries, including agriculture, food, pharmaceuticals, and bulk chemicals. The popularity of pneumatic conveying in industry has increased over the last few decades due to its potential advantages compared to alternative material transport approaches such as lower initial cost, ease of automation, minimal product degradation, and reduced need for maintenance [1]. The flow modes in pneumatic conveying systems can generally be divided into two broad categories: dilute phase flow, in which particles are suspended in a gas stream, and dense phase flow at lower velocities.

Various dense phase conveying modes can arise depending on the material characteristics, pipeline geometry and operational conditions [2]. In plug flow, permeable granular materials are transported as discrete particle plugs, separated by air pockets in between [3]. These plugs dynamically exchange particles with the stationary particle layer in front of and behind them, picking up particles at the front and depositing particles at the rear of each plug [4]. At steady state, these two phenomena occur at equal rates, and plugs of fixed length travel along the pipe.

Considerable experimental research has been done on pneumatic conveying in plug flow mode. However, it is difficult to obtain microscopic data from physical experiments, which is an advantage of numerical simulations. There are two main types of numerical models used to simulate pneumatic conveying. The first type, the Two-Fluid Model (TFM), is an Eulerian–Eulerian model, in which both solid and fluid phases are treated as interpenetrating continuous media. TFM requires the adoption of constitutive models at bulk level in order to close the governing equations [2]. Because of its computational efficiency it has been used to simulate various flow modes (dilute phase [5–7] and dense phase [8–10]) and pipe geometries (vertical [6, 11], inclined [12], bend [9,13] and horizontal [5,8,14]). The increased availability of substantial computational resources has encouraged a second, more computationally expensive model to emerge and become widespread: Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Discrete Element Method (DEM) coupled simulations (CFD–DEM simulations). In this method, the fluid phase is modelled as an Eulerian field, while the solid phase is modelled as discrete (Lagrangian) particles. The interactions between the particles are represented by the popular soft-sphere DEM approach [15]. TFM is particularly suited for large systems but lacks the understanding of fundamental interaction at the particle level. By contrast, CFD–DEM is much more computationally intensive but gives a deeper understanding at the micro-scale [2].

CFD–DEM has been used to explore horizontal pneumatic conveying since the pioneering work of Tsuji et al. [16]. For plug flow conveying, Kuang et al. [17] investigated how some plug parameters (e.g., plug length and velocity) and micro- and macro-behaviour are affected by gas velocity. Since CFD–DEM is a computationally expensive method, in another study, Kuang et al. [18] investigated the application of periodic boundary conditions (PBC) in horizontal plug flow. The effect of friction and restitution coefficients in DEM on the flow modes and plug parameters were studied by Li et al. [19]. In an experimental and numerical study, Zhou et al. [20] investigated plug flow conveying and confirmed that plugs are continuously updated and rolled forward. Lavrinec et al. [21,22] found that plugs reach a steady-state length that depends on the air velocity and stationary layer height.

All of these studies were restricted to spherical particles, even though a large majority of particles used in industrial applications are

non-spherical. Moreover, the packing characteristics of non-spherical particles, which has a crucial influence on plug flow conveying, differ considerably from those of spherical particles [23,24]. Hilton and Cleary [25] explored the impact of particle shape on flow patterns in dense phase pneumatic conveying by using superquadric particles in an infinite parallel-plate geometry. It was concluded that spherical or nearly spherical particles tend to form plugs at high gas flow rates, while non-spherical particles tend to flow in a fully dilute mode. Furthermore, Kruggel-Emden and Oschmann [26], Oschmann et al. [27] and Markauskas et al. [28] examined the rope formation, dispersion and mixing of non-spherical particles while passing through a pipe bend. Their results indicate that the pressure drop, particle velocity distribution, rope dispersion and mixing are strongly influenced by particle shape. Breakage [29,30] and pickup characteristics [31] in pneumatic conveying have also been studied in the context of non-spherical particles, and the effects of particle shape were found to be considerable.

Despite its importance, the effect of particle shape and its interactions with the particle size, pipe pressure gradient, and contact parameters have never been studied in a robust way in horizontal plug flow pneumatic conveying in pipes of circular cross-section, to the best of the authors' knowledge. In this paper, we fill this knowledge gap using 3D CFD–DEM coupled simulations with ellipsoidal particles. In particular, we have conducted a comprehensive analysis on the effect of particle shape, particle size, particle contact parameters, and pressure gradient imposed longitudinally along the pipe on plug flow behaviour. We show not only the main effects of these parameters on plug flow conveying, but also their interactions with the particle shape. Furthermore, the results have some important implications for CFD–DEM modellers working on similar flow conditions, which can ease and speed up the modelling process. To do so, a 1-m-long rigid, cylindrical pipe is used with periodic boundary conditions at inlet and outlet, representing a section of a much longer pipe. The ranges of flow and particle parameters are chosen to ensure that plugs are always formed. As plug flow is a widely observed mode of flow in various industries, it is expected that understanding the interplay between the operational and particle parameters will enable improvements of the design and operation of pneumatic conveyors.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. The mathematical formulation and the numerical methods are discussed in Section 2. The simulation conditions and experimental design are described in Section 3. The simulation results are presented and discussed in Section 4, before concluding in Section 5.

2. Numerical methods and model formulation

DEM and CFD equations are solved using the commercial Aspherix software (Version 6.1.0) and the open-source OpenFOAM software (Version 8), respectively, linked via the CFDEMCoupling framework (non-spherical Version 6.1.0) [32,33]. The details of the formulation and numerical methods of DEM and CFD are explained in the following sections.

2.1. Discrete element method (DEM)

The discrete element method (DEM) is a computational technique used to simulate the motions of and interactions between individual particles. In the present study, a soft-sphere DEM model is used, where

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the solid phase is represented by Lagrangian particles [15]. The governing equation describing the translational motion of particle i can be given as:

$$m_i \frac{d\mathbf{v}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{F}_{pgf,i} + \mathbf{F}_{hf,i} + \sum_j (\mathbf{F}_{ij,n} + \mathbf{F}_{ij,t}) + m_i \mathbf{g}, \quad (1)$$

where the subscript j represents the particles in contact with particle i . The mass and translational velocity of particle i are denoted by m_i and \mathbf{v}_i , respectively. The gravitational acceleration is \mathbf{g} . The pressure gradient force, total hydrodynamic force, normal and tangential contact forces are represented by $\mathbf{F}_{pgf,i}$, $\mathbf{F}_{hf,i}$, $\mathbf{F}_{ij,n}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{ij,t}$, respectively. The total hydrodynamic force consists of the drag force and lift force which are discussed in detail in Section 2.2. The normal and tangential contact forces are calculated as $\mathbf{F}_{ij,n} = k_n \delta_{n,ij} \hat{\mathbf{n}} - \gamma_n \mathbf{v}_{n,ij}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{ij,t} = k_t \delta_{t,ij} \hat{\mathbf{t}} - \gamma_t \mathbf{v}_{t,ij}$, where k , δ_n , δ_t , γ and \mathbf{v} are the spring stiffness, normal overlap, tangential displacement, damping constant and relative velocity, respectively. Subscripts “n” and “t” denote the normal and tangential directions. A nonlinear contact model is used in the simulations, so the spring stiffnesses and damping constants for the normal and tangential forces have a dependence on the normal overlap:

$$k_n = \frac{4}{3} Y^* \sqrt{r^* \delta_n}, \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma_n = -2 \sqrt{\frac{5}{6}} \beta \sqrt{S_n m^*},$$

$$k_t = 8G^* \sqrt{r^* \delta_n}, \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_t = -2 \sqrt{\frac{5}{6}} \beta \sqrt{S_t m^*}.$$

The parameters appearing in the calculations of spring stiffnesses and damping coefficients are defined as:

$$\frac{1}{Y^*} = \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{Y_i} + \frac{1 - \nu_j^2}{Y_j}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{1}{r^*} = \frac{1}{r_i} + \frac{1}{r_j}, \quad (5)$$

$$\beta = \frac{\ln e}{\sqrt{\ln e^2 + \pi^2}}, \quad (6)$$

$$S_n = 2Y^* \sqrt{r^* \delta_n}, \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{m^*} = \frac{1}{m_i} + \frac{1}{m_j}, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{1}{G^*} = \frac{2(2 - \nu_i)(1 + \nu_j)}{Y_i} + \frac{2(2 - \nu_j)(1 + \nu_i)}{Y_j}, \quad (9)$$

$$S_t = 2G^* \sqrt{r^* \delta_n}, \quad (10)$$

where Y , G , ν , r , e , m are the Young's modulus, shear modulus, Poisson's ratio, particle radius, coefficient of restitution, and mass, respectively. In the calculation of the tangential force, the tangential displacement is determined by integrating the relative tangential velocity at the contact point, so it has the “history” effect from the previous time steps. A Coulomb criterion is applied to limit the magnitude of the tangential force: $F_{ij,t} \leq \mu F_{ij,n}$, with μ as the sliding friction coefficient. The same contact model is applied to particles in contact with rigid walls.

The rotational motion of particle i is obtained by solving the following equation:

$$I_i \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}_i}{dt} = \sum_j (\mathbf{T}_{c,ij} + \mathbf{T}_{r,ij} + \mathbf{T}_{f,i}), \quad (11)$$

where subscript j again represents the particles in contact with particle i . The moment of inertia and rotational velocity of particle i are I_i and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$, respectively. The contact torque on particle i due to particle j is denoted by $\mathbf{T}_{c,ij}$. For non-spherical particles, both normal and tangential contact forces contribute to the calculation of contact torque. The rolling friction torque, $\mathbf{T}_{r,ij}$, is modelled by a widely used elastic-plastic spring-dashpot model proposed by Iwashita and Oda [34], implemented as the “epsd2” rolling friction model in Aspherix. The

Fig. 1. Example oblate and prolate ellipsoids and their aspect ratios according to the definition used in the present work.

fluid-induced torque on the particle is $\mathbf{T}_{f,i}$. In the present study, it is represented by the pitching torque and Stokesian rotational drag which are described in Section 2.2.

Superquadric particles provide a means of representing a wide variety of non-spherical particle shapes in DEM. Their implementation and contact detection is described by Podlozhnyuk et al. [35]. Superquadrics are described by [36]:

$$f(x, y, z) = \left(\left| \frac{x}{a} \right|^{n_2} + \left| \frac{y}{b} \right|^{n_2} \right)^{n_1/n_2} + \left| \frac{z}{c} \right|^{n_1} - 1 = 0. \quad (12)$$

Here, a , b , and c are the half-lengths of a superquadric particle along its principal axes, and n_1 and n_2 are the blockiness parameters. These can be used to control the shape of the particle and represent different shapes such as spheres, rounded cubes and cylinders, and even more complex shapes. In this work, ellipsoids and spheres are used to investigate the effect of particle shape. An ellipsoid can be obtained from Eq. (12) by setting $n_1 = n_2 = 2$. Two examples of ellipsoids are given in Fig. 1. In the present work, the aspect ratio of an ellipsoid is defined from its constructing ellipse, so it is the ratio of the axis of rotation of the ellipse to its other axis. For an oblate ellipsoid, it is the ratio of its minor axis to major axis, and for a prolate ellipsoid, vice versa. Therefore, the oblate ellipsoid in Fig. 1 has an aspect ratio of 0.5 (AR = 0.5), while the prolate one has AR = 2.0.

2.2. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD)

Gas flow is considered as a continuous phase. As described by Zhou et al. [37], there exist three distinct formulations in the literature for this purpose. The current study uses the formulation known as “Model A”. Incompressible volume-averaged Navier–Stokes equations are solved using PISO pressure–velocity coupling to obtain the velocity and pressure fields [38]. Then, this information is used to calculate the fluid forces and torques on the particles and communicated to the DEM solver. Finally, the new positions and velocities of the particles are calculated according to the net forces, these are sent back to the CFD solver, and the loop continues. More details of the CFD–DEM algorithm can be found in Kloss et al. [39] and Goniva et al. [33].

The momentum and continuity equations for the fluid phase are given as:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_f}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \mathbf{u}_f) = 0, \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\alpha_f \mathbf{u}_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{u}_f) = -\alpha_f \nabla \frac{p}{\rho_f} - \mathbf{R}_{pf} + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \alpha_f \mathbf{g}, \quad (14)$$

where α_f , ρ_f , \mathbf{u}_f , and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ are the fluid volume fraction, density, velocity, and stress tensor. \mathbf{R}_{pf} represents the momentum exchange between the

fluid and the particles. It is calculated for each cell in the system, and it is assembled from the fluid forces on individual particles. The drag, lift and hydrodynamic torque models used in the momentum exchange are explained in detail in the following subsections. It should be noted that in dense phase systems including rather coarse particles, such as the one examined here, the effect of turbulence is negligible [40]. Therefore, a turbulence model is not included in the present study. The “divided” model, which is integrated into Aspherix, is utilised for void fraction calculations for both spherical and superquadric particles. Rather than allocating the entire volume of a particle to the cell containing the particle centre, this model apportions the particle volume among the CFD cells that contain it. As a result, when a particle is the same size as a CFD cell or its centre is close to the edge of a CFD cell and overlaps with a neighbouring cell, the model distributes the particle volume among these nearby cells. This means that particles occupying multiple grid cells are considered correctly in the void fraction calculations.

2.2.1. Drag force

The drag force plays a very important role in the modelling of dense particulate flow systems. The drag force on a single particle can be described by:

$$F_{DO} = \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho_f A_{\perp} |\mathbf{u}_r| \mathbf{u}_r, \quad (15)$$

where C_D , A_{\perp} , and \mathbf{u}_r are the drag coefficient, cross-sectional area of the particle relative to the fluid flow, and the relative fluid flow vector, respectively. The relative fluid flow vector is calculated as the difference between the fluid velocity vector in the corresponding CFD cell and the particle velocity, i.e., $\mathbf{u}_r = \mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{v}_i$.

However, in dense phase solid flows, the effect of neighbouring particles on the particle drag should also be taken into account. Therefore, in the present study, the void fraction correction model introduced by Di Felice [41] is used. The drag force on the particle becomes $F_D = F_{DO} a_f^{2-\chi}$, where χ is given by:

$$\chi = 3.7 - 0.65 \exp \left[-0.5 (1.5 - \log Re_p)^2 \right]. \quad (16)$$

Here, $Re_p = \frac{\rho_f d_v \mathbf{u}_r}{\eta_f}$ denotes the particle Reynolds number where η_f is the fluid viscosity, and d_v is the diameter of the sphere of the same volume as the corresponding non-spherical particle.

Although many models for the drag coefficient have been proposed in literature, few of them are applicable to non-spherical particles, and most of those are valid for specific Re_p intervals and particle shapes and include many fitting parameters [42–44]. By contrast, the model proposed by Hölzer and Sommerfeld [45], developed using experimental data, is widely used for dense gas–solid flows, and it gives reasonably good approximations for a wide range of Re_p and particle shapes [25,40,46]. Therefore, this model has been utilised in the present study:

$$C_D = \frac{8}{Re_p} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Phi_{\perp}}} + \frac{16}{Re_p} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Phi}} + \frac{3}{\sqrt{Re_p}} \frac{1}{\Phi^{3/4}} + 0.42 \times 10^{0.4(-\log \Phi)^{0.2}} \frac{1}{\Phi_{\perp}}, \quad (17)$$

where Φ is the particle sphericity and Φ_{\perp} is the crosswise sphericity. The crosswise sphericity is defined as the ratio of the cross-sectional area of a sphere with the same volume as the particle, A , to the cross-sectional area of the particle as projected onto a plane perpendicular to the flow, A_{\perp} , i.e., $\Phi_{\perp} = A/A_{\perp}$. This term enables this drag model to take particle orientation into account in the drag coefficient calculation.

2.2.2. Lift force

A lift force on a non-spherical particle arises when the particle is not fully aligned with or perpendicular to the flow because the symmetry of the flow around the particle is broken. This induces a pressure difference on both sides of the particle and results in a shape-induced

lift force [46]. A common assumption is that the lift force on a non-spherical particle is proportional to the drag force and is caused by the orientation of the particle relative to the flow. This is known as the “cross flow principle” and was first proposed by Hoerner [47]. According to this rule, the lift coefficient C_L is formulated as:

$$\frac{C_L}{C_D} = \sin^2 \varphi \cos \varphi, \quad (18)$$

where φ is the angle of incidence, defined as the angle between the major axis of the particle and the relative fluid flow vector, \mathbf{u}_r .

The magnitude of the lift force for a single particle without any neighbouring particles is calculated using the following expression:

$$F_{LO} = \frac{1}{2} C_L \rho_f \frac{\pi}{4} d_v^2 |\mathbf{u}_r|^2. \quad (19)$$

The effect of the neighbouring particles is neglected in the calculation of the lift force, i.e., the lift force is not corrected using Di Felice’s correlation as the drag force is. Therefore, the lift force magnitude is $F_L = F_{LO}$. The orientation of the lift force is given by Mema et al. [46] as:

$$\hat{e}_L = \frac{\mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}_r}{|\mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}_r|} \frac{(\mathbf{v}_i \times \mathbf{u}_r) \times \mathbf{u}_r}{|(\mathbf{v}_i \times \mathbf{u}_r) \times \mathbf{u}_r|}. \quad (20)$$

Therefore, the final lift force vector on the particle is calculated as $F_L = F_L \hat{e}_L$.

2.2.3. Hydrodynamic torque

When a particle attains a certain angle relative to the fluid flow, its centre of pressure also changes based on the angle of incidence [48]. Therefore, its centre of mass and centre of pressure no longer coincide. This gives rise to an additional torque on the particle which is called the pitching torque or hydrodynamic torque. Particles also experience a rotational drag when they spin, which can be approximated using the Stokesian rotational drag model. Hence, in this study, the fluid-induced torque on each particle is computed using the models for these two phenomena: $T_f = T_p + T_D$, where T_p and T_D are the pitching torque and Stokesian rotational drag, respectively.

The pitching torque is modelled using the cross-flow principle [49]:

$$\frac{C_T}{C_D} = \sin \varphi \cos \varphi, \quad (21)$$

where C_T is the torque coefficient. Once C_T is obtained, the magnitude of the pitching torque can be calculated as:

$$T_p = \frac{1}{2} C_T \rho_f \frac{\pi}{8} d_v^3 |\mathbf{u}_r|^2. \quad (22)$$

The direction of the pitching torque is given by [46]:

$$\hat{e}_{PT} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_r \cdot \mathbf{v}_i}{|\mathbf{u}_r \cdot \mathbf{v}_i|} \frac{\mathbf{u}_r \times \mathbf{v}_i}{|\mathbf{u}_r \times \mathbf{v}_i|}. \quad (23)$$

The pitching torque vector can be calculated by multiplying its magnitude and direction: $T_p = T_p \hat{e}_{PT}$.

The Stokesian rotational drag term, which represents the effect of surrounding gas on a rotating particle, is given by [25]:

$$T_D = \pi \eta_f d_v^3 \omega_r. \quad (24)$$

Here, $\omega_r = \omega_f - \omega_i$ denotes the spin of the particle relative to its surrounding fluid, where ω_f and ω_i are the spin of the fluid and particle, respectively.

An individual plug in pneumatic conveying can also be considered as a moving particle bed, so it is important to be able to correctly predict the pressure drop across a particle bed for plug flow pneumatic conveying simulations. Therefore, the numerical model was first tested against the theoretical relation of Ergun [50]. A particle bed was formed in an Ergun test simulation, and the analytical fluidisation curve was able to be captured with the present model. Then, the model was further compared with the CFD–DEM simulations of Hilton and Cleary [25] in dense phase pneumatic conveying. It was seen that as the pressure gradient was increased, the obtained particle behaviour was in good agreement with that observed by Hilton and Cleary [25].

Fig. 2. The geometry of the pipe including the CFD mesh shown by blue lines.

3. Simulation conditions and experimental design

Plug flow conveying is examined in a horizontal, cylindrical and rigid pipe with periodic boundary conditions in the axial direction. The pipe length and internal diameter are 1.0 m and 0.05 m, respectively. The illustration of the pipe geometry with CFD mesh, its dimensions, and the direction of the imposed pressure gradient is given in Fig. 2. The conveying fluid is incompressible air. Particles are considered cohesionless throughout the study. Simulations are run in accordance with a two-stage design of experiments. In the first stage, the effects of particle size d_v , imposed pressure gradient $|\nabla p|$, p-p (particle-particle) and p-w (particle-wall) sliding friction coefficients μ_{p-p} and μ_{p-w} , p-p and p-w rolling friction coefficients $\mu_{r,p-p}$ and $\mu_{r,p-w}$, and p-p and p-w restitution coefficients e_{p-p} and e_{p-w} are compared in a fractional factorial design with eight factors, using two levels for each, requiring 16 simulations to be run. In these simulations, particle shape is kept constant as a prolate ellipsoid with $AR = 1.5$. It should be noted that during the preliminary simulations, various parameters including Young's modulus were also tested. However, their impact on the response parameters was found to be comparatively less significant than the parameters encompassed in this design of experiments study. Therefore, their effects are not studied further in the present work.

The results of this screening study are then used to create a three-level Taguchi design with five factors and 27 simulation runs, where particle shape is compared against the four factors identified as significant in the first stage of the simulations. In these simulations, the effect of particle shape is included by varying the aspect ratio of the ellipsoid while keeping its volume the same. The parameters and their levels in the first and second stages are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. All simulations performed as part of these fractional factorial and Taguchi designs are summarised in Tables 3 and 4, respectively. Minitab® Statistical Software is used in the planning of the numerical experiments and analysis of the results.

The plug response is characterised in terms of plug length (L_{plug}), velocity (U_{plug}), porosity (ϵ_{plug}), and particle exchange rate (λ). The new parameter — “particle exchange rate” — is defined as the percentage of the plug particles exchanged with the stationary layer per second. An increasing particle exchange rate indicates that particles are less likely to stay as a plug and more likely to roll over each other to the stationary layer. Therefore, this response indicates the stability of the plug. This terminology is used throughout the paper. Fig. 3 shows how a plug is defined. This is done by identifying the particles that are located above $y = 0.86R$, where R is the pipe radius and $y = 0$ is at the centreline of the pipe. This threshold is chosen so that a further increase does not alter the obtained plug properties significantly. Then, those two particles above this threshold which are furthest apart in the z direction are determined. Finally, the plug is defined as all the particles between

Fig. 3. The definition of a plug (magenta) with the four response parameters: plug length (L_{plug}), velocity (U_{plug}), porosity (ϵ_{plug}), and particle exchange rate (λ).

Table 1

Parameters considered in the first stage of the simulations: fractional factorial design with eight factors and two levels (16 simulations).

Factor	Low	High
Particle volume-equivalent diameter (d_v) [mm]	3.0	3.8
Pressure gradient ($ \nabla p $) [kPa m^{-1}]	2.7	3.6
p-p sliding friction coefficient (μ_{p-p})	0.1	0.5
p-w sliding friction coefficient (μ_{p-w})	0.24	0.28
p-p rolling friction coefficient ($\mu_{r,p-p}$)	0.0	0.2
p-w rolling friction coefficient ($\mu_{r,p-w}$)	0.0	0.2
p-p coefficient of restitution (e_{p-p})	0.5	0.9
p-w coefficient of restitution (e_{p-w})	0.5	0.9

Table 2

Parameters considered in the second stage of the simulations: Taguchi design with five factors and three levels (27 simulations).

Factor	Low	Medium	High
Particle aspect ratio (AR)	0.5	1.0	2.0
Pressure gradient ($ \nabla p $) [kPa m^{-1}]	2.7	3.15	3.6
p-p sliding friction coefficient (μ_{p-p})	0.1	0.3	0.5
p-w sliding friction coefficient (μ_{p-w})	0.24	0.26	0.28
p-p rolling friction coefficient ($\mu_{r,p-p}$)	0.0	0.1	0.2

these two points. Plug velocity, porosity, and length are calculated in this plug region.

Throughout the study, those parameters listed in Table 5 are kept fixed. All simulations are initialised by filling the pipe with particles up to the half-way point. The number of particles may thus change between the simulations as particle shape and size are not constant. However, the total particle mass does not vary significantly. Once the particles have been generated, the flow is started by imposing a

Table 3

The summary of the simulations performed in the first stage of the simulations: fractional factorial design with eight factors and two levels (16 simulations).

Simulation	d_v [mm]	$ \nabla p $ [kPa m ⁻¹]	μ_{p-p}	μ_{p-w}	$\mu_{r,p-p}$	$\mu_{r,p-w}$	e_{p-p}	e_{p-w}
1	3	2.7	0.1	0.24	0	0	0.5	0.5
2	3.8	2.7	0.1	0.24	0	0.2	0.9	0.9
3	3	3.6	0.1	0.24	0.2	0	0.9	0.9
4	3.8	3.6	0.1	0.24	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.5
5	3	2.7	0.5	0.24	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.5
6	3.8	2.7	0.5	0.24	0.2	0	0.5	0.9
7	3	3.6	0.5	0.24	0	0.2	0.5	0.9
8	3.8	3.6	0.5	0.24	0	0	0.9	0.5
9	3	2.7	0.1	0.28	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.9
10	3.8	2.7	0.1	0.28	0.2	0	0.9	0.5
11	3	3.6	0.1	0.28	0	0.2	0.9	0.5
12	3.8	3.6	0.1	0.28	0	0	0.5	0.9
13	3	2.7	0.5	0.28	0	0	0.9	0.9
14	3.8	2.7	0.5	0.28	0	0.2	0.5	0.5
15	3	3.6	0.5	0.28	0.2	0	0.5	0.5
16	3.8	3.6	0.5	0.28	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.9

Table 4

The summary of the simulations performed in the second stage of the simulations: Taguchi design with five factors and three levels (27 simulations).

Simulation	AR	$ \nabla p $ [kPa m ⁻¹]	μ_{p-p}	μ_{p-w}	$\mu_{r,p-p}$
1	0.5	2.7	0.1	0.24	0
2	0.5	2.7	0.3	0.26	0.1
3	0.5	2.7	0.5	0.28	0.2
4	0.5	3.15	0.1	0.26	0.2
5	0.5	3.15	0.3	0.28	0
6	0.5	3.15	0.5	0.24	0.1
7	0.5	3.6	0.1	0.28	0.1
8	0.5	3.6	0.3	0.24	0.2
9	0.5	3.6	0.5	0.26	0
10	1	2.7	0.1	0.24	0
11	1	2.7	0.3	0.26	0.1
12	1	2.7	0.5	0.28	0.2
13	1	3.15	0.1	0.26	0.2
14	1	3.15	0.3	0.28	0
15	1	3.15	0.5	0.24	0.1
16	1	3.6	0.1	0.28	0.1
17	1	3.6	0.3	0.24	0.2
18	1	3.6	0.5	0.26	0
19	2	2.7	0.1	0.24	0
20	2	2.7	0.3	0.26	0.1
21	2	2.7	0.5	0.28	0.2
22	2	3.15	0.1	0.26	0.2
23	2	3.15	0.3	0.28	0
24	2	3.15	0.5	0.24	0.1
25	2	3.6	0.1	0.28	0.1
26	2	3.6	0.3	0.24	0.2
27	2	3.6	0.5	0.26	0

constant pressure gradient along the pipe. The responses are calculated once the steady state is reached by averaging their values over the last 2 s of the simulation, using data output at intervals of 0.05 s. The particle aspect ratio is kept constant at AR = 1.5 in the screening stage, but it is included in the second stage of the analysis and its effects on plug flow are analysed. The parameter intervals are chosen so that stable plugs can form with any combination of the parameter levels. For example, while keeping the other parameters within the specified intervals, if the p-w sliding friction coefficient were increased beyond 0.28, the plug formed may block the pipe. If it were decreased below 0.24, then the plug may never reach a steady state.

The unresolved CFD-DEM formulation requires the CFD grid size to be larger than the particle dimensions while ensuring the grid-independence of the CFD solution. The simulations performed in this paper have been set up so that the CFD grid size is always larger than the largest and longest particle, allowing free rotation within the cell when the particle is placed at the centre of the cell [46]. Moreover, the effect of grid size on plug velocity, plug length and plug

Table 5

Fixed CFD and DEM parameters throughout the study.

Parameter	Value
Pipe and CFD properties	
Pipe length (L_2) [m]	1.0
Pipe diameter (D) [m]	0.05
Number of CFD cells (N)	7680
Fluid density (ρ_f) [kg m ⁻³]	1.2
Fluid viscosity (η_f) [Pa s]	1.8×10^{-5}
CFD time step (Δt_{CFD}) [s]	10^{-4}
Particle and DEM properties	
Particle density (ρ_p) [kg m ⁻³]	1000
Young's modulus (E) [Pa]	1.0×10^7
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.33
DEM time step (Δt_{DEM}) [s]	1.0×10^{-5}

porosity (void fraction) have been checked; the relative error for these quantities is less than 3% when the grid size is doubled, which indicates that the present results are grid-independent. Although the particle can rotate freely in a cell, the grid size and particle length become comparable in the simulations with the longest and largest particles: an undesirable scenario for unresolved CFD-DEM simulations in which the particle size needs to be sufficiently small compared to the CFD grid size. To mitigate this, a smoothing algorithm is used throughout this study which involves solving an additional diffusion equation as $\partial\psi/\partial t - (L_{smooth}^2/\Delta t_{CFD})\nabla^2\psi = 0$, where ψ is the smoothed exchange field, such as void fraction, and L_{smooth} is the smoothing length that is defined as $L_{smooth} = 1.5d_v$ in the present study [51].

Burns et al. [52] derived critical time steps for the normal and tangential directions for DEM simulations with the Hertzian contact model and a dynamic system of spherical particles. The minimum of these critical time steps should be considered when deciding the time step for DEM simulations. Based on this analysis, the minimum critical time step is $\Delta t_{c, \min} = 2.42 \times 10^{-5}$ s for the smallest particle investigated in this study ($d_v = 3.0$ mm). The Rayleigh time step for this same particle is $\Delta t_r = 8.26 \times 10^{-5}$ s. The effect of particle aspect ratio on the critical time step for a linear contact model was given by Peng et al. [53]. As the aspect ratio of the particles increase, the critical time step decreases. However, this effect only becomes significant when the aspect ratio is larger than 2.0: the maximum aspect ratio examined in the present study. Considering all these effects and applying a safety factor, the DEM time step in the present simulations is chosen as $\Delta t_{DEM} = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$ s.

4. Results and discussion

Firstly, in Section 4.1, a typical plug flow conveying process is explained using the base case parameters. This baseline case is defined as $d_v = 3.4$ mm, $|\nabla p| = 3.0$ kPa m⁻¹, $\mu_{p-p} = 0.3$, $\mu_{p-w} = 0.26$, $\mu_{r,p-p} = \mu_{r,p-w} = 0.1$, and $e_{p-p} = e_{p-w} = 0.7$ using ellipsoids with AR = 1.5. Then, in Section 4.2, the most influential parameters on the process of plug flow conveying are determined using a fractional factorial analysis with eight factors and two levels. The parameters included in this analysis are given in Table 1. The particle aspect ratio is fixed at 1.5 at this stage because the main purpose is to eliminate the least influential parameters, and it is well known that shape is highly influential. The most influential parameters, including particle shape, are then investigated in the second stage of the analysis using a five-factor, three-level Taguchi design as summarised in Table 2 and Table 4.

4.1. Dynamics of plug flow conveying process

Plug flow conveying is a dynamic process, where particles are continuously dropped from the rear of the plug and picked up from the stationary layer at the front [2,17,20,54,55]. In this subsection, this dynamic process is briefly explained.

Fig. 4. Evolution of a plug at steady state of the baseline case simulation ($d_v = 3.4$ mm, AR = 1.5 (prolate ellipsoid), $|\nabla p| = 3.0$ kPa m $^{-1}$, $\mu_{p-p} = 0.3$, $\mu_{p-w} = 0.26$, $\mu_{r,p-p} = 0.1$, $\mu_{r,p-w} = 0.1$, $e_{p-p} = 0.7$, $e_{p-w} = 0.7$). The particles in the system are colour-coded based on their location at time $t = t_0$. Magenta particles are in the plug, blue particles are in the upper part of the stationary bed, and black particles are in the lower part of the stationary bed.

Three snapshots from the steady state of the baseline case simulation are given in Fig. 4, where the y and z coordinates are aligned with the vertical and horizontal axes, respectively. After the flow begins, steady state is reached after around 8 s. The snapshots indicate how a plug, moving in the $+z$ -direction, is transported along the periodic pipe in a single pass. The particles in the system initially are divided into three zones, represented by colour on Fig. 4. Magenta represents the particles in the plug in the uppermost snapshot, blue is for the particles in the upper part of the stationary bed, and the black particles are those in the lower part of the stationary bed. The evolution of these particle locations within this plug can be tracked from the middle and bottom snapshots. As stated earlier, the plug loses particles from its rear, so some of the magenta particles in the plug join the stationary bed behind the plug. The blue and black particles from the stationary bed both join the plug at the front; the former are incorporated into the upper section of the newly formed plug while the latter form the lower section. This observation is in line with the experimental results reported by Takei et al. [56]. At steady state, this dynamic behaviour reaches an equilibrium, where the numbers of particles joining and leaving the plug are balanced so the plug length fluctuates around a mean value.

A snapshot of the particles from the baseline case simulation at $t = 9.55$ s is given in Fig. 5a. The corresponding spatial distributions of the void fraction (b), pressure (c), and z - and y - components (d and e) of the solid velocity ($u_{s,y}$ and $u_{s,z}$) are also presented in Fig. 5. Since the simulations are 3-D, these spatial distributions are given on a plane that intersects the domain at $x = 0.0$ in the y - z plane. Fig. 5b depicts the void fraction distribution, where the plug and the stationary bed

correspond to the blue region due to their lower void fraction values. Fig. 5c shows that the pressure along the plug increases linearly from the front to the rear, in agreement with the observations of Hilton and Cleary [25] and Kuang and Yu [55]. An almost constant velocity distribution within the plug is evident in Fig. 5d and e. However, this does not hold for the rear and front of the plug as particle exchange occurs at these regions. In fact, Fig. 5d indicates that particles gradually slow down at the plug rear as they are dropped onto the stationary layer and reach zero velocity. Particles form a tip at the plug front, where particle velocities reach their maxima, in agreement with Zhou et al. [20]. Fig. 4 suggests that this occurs due to the avalanche of the particles at the plug front over the stationary layer of particles in front of the plug. This tip region can be seen more clearly in Fig. 5e, where the red colour indicates the upward solid velocity (particle pick-up) and blue the downward solid velocity (particle deposition). This plug tip, where the maximum solid velocity is observed, coincides with this avalanche region. Within the plug, the solid velocity is distributed homogeneously, where $u_{s,y} \approx 0.0$ and $u_{s,z} \approx 1.45$ m s $^{-1}$.

4.2. First stage of simulations

In the first of the two stages of the design of experiments study, a fractional factorial design with eight factors and two levels is created. Four responses are investigated: the plug length, plug velocity, plug porosity, and particle exchange rate.

Fig. 6 presents the Pareto chart and main effects plot for the particle exchange rate. The statistically significant parameters at the 95% confidence level for particle exchange rate are p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients, pressure gradient, p-w sliding friction coefficient and p-w rolling friction coefficient, with the first two having the greatest influence and the last of these being barely significant. The main effects plot shows that μ_{p-w} is directly proportional to the particle exchange rate, while the other significant parameters are inversely proportional. Particle-particle interactions play an important role in the communication between the plug and stationary layer, and the main source of interaction is the sliding and rolling of particles over each other rather than direct impact. Therefore, the larger observed effects of μ_{p-p} and $\mu_{r,p-p}$ on the particle exchange rate are consistent with the mechanism of plug conveying in the pipe.

The results for plug velocity, U_{plug} , are given in Fig. 7. The Pareto chart illustrates that the p-w sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-w} , pressure gradient $|\nabla p|$, p-p rolling friction coefficient $\mu_{r,p-p}$, and p-p sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-p} have a statistically significant effect. As the pressure gradient, p-p sliding or p-p rolling friction coefficients increase, the plug velocity also increases, while increasing the p-w sliding friction coefficient has the opposite effect. The effect of pressure gradient and p-w sliding friction coefficient on the response is intuitive, but it is somewhat counterintuitive to see that U_{plug} increases with increasing μ_{p-p} and $\mu_{r,p-p}$ as the particles are expected to dissipate more energy at interparticle contacts as these parameters increase. However, Fig. 6 shows that the rate of particle exchange decreases with increasing μ_{p-p} and $\mu_{r,p-p}$. Therefore, consideration of both results indicates that the plugs are more stable and the overall energy dissipation is less in high μ_{p-p} and $\mu_{r,p-p}$ cases, although the energy dissipation from a single particle-particle contact may be higher. Another reason is that as the particle exchange rate increases, more particles join the plug from the stationary layer. These must be accelerated from zero velocity, which eventually results in a slower overall steady state plug velocity. Li et al. [19] reported in their numerical study of horizontal pneumatic conveying with spherical particles that increasing the sliding friction coefficient results in a decrease in slug velocity. However, they did not use different values for p-p and p-w sliding friction coefficients. In the present study, it is shown that p-p and p-w sliding friction coefficients have opposite effects on the plug velocity. On the other hand, it is

Fig. 5. (a) A snapshot from the baseline case (with prolate ellipsoids) simulation at $t = 9.55$ s, and the corresponding spatial distributions of (b) void fraction, (c) pressure, (d) z-component of the solid velocity, and (e) y-component of the solid velocity. The slice is taken at $x = 0.0$ in the $y-z$ plane.

Fig. 6. First stage of simulations. Pareto chart and main effects plot for particle exchange rate.

Fig. 7. First stage of simulations. Pareto chart and main effects plot for plug velocity.

Fig. 8. First stage of simulations. Pareto chart and main effects plot for plug length.

also shown that p-w sliding friction is a more significant parameter for the plug velocity, although it is examined in a narrower interval. As a result, it can be concluded that the findings align with those previously reported by Li et al. [19], where the decreasing plug velocity can be attributed to the greater influence of the p-w sliding friction over the plug length compared to the p-p sliding friction, as the Pareto chart in Fig. 7 indicates.

Plug length, L_{plug} , is one of the important plug parameters that is usually reported in plug flow pneumatic conveying research. Thus, it has been examined as another response parameter in this study. Fig. 8 shows the Pareto chart and main effects plot for the plug length. The results indicate that the significant parameters are p-p sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-p} , p-p rolling friction coefficient $\mu_{r,p-p}$, pressure gradient $|\nabla p|$, and p-w sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-w} . It should be noted that this order is exactly the same as it was for the particle exchange rate. Among these significant parameters, as the p-w sliding friction coefficient increases, the plug length decreases, and vice versa for the other parameters. It is not surprising to see that p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients affect the results in the same way as both are related to energy dissipation. Furthermore, as the pressure gradient increases, more particles are picked up from the stationary layer and join the plug, so the plug length increases.

The last response considered in this section is the plug porosity, ϵ_{plug} . Plugs can be considered as packed moving beds, which have a slightly higher porosity than the porosity of a stationary particle bed [54]. Therefore, plug porosity plays a crucial role in drag force and pressure drop along the plug. The Pareto chart and main effect plots are presented in Fig. 9. These demonstrate that the p-p sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-p} and p-p rolling friction coefficient $\mu_{r,p-p}$ are the significant parameters, and they are both directly proportional to the plug porosity. This confirms the well-known result that particles are packed less tightly as friction increases [57,58]. The results also confirm that the plug porosity is independent of the air velocity, as shown previously by Lecreps et al. [54].

It is noteworthy that the imposed pressure gradient, hence the air velocity, does not have the highest standardised effect for any of the four response parameters. Even for the plug velocity, which can

Fig. 9. First stage of simulations. Pareto chart and main effects plot for plug porosity.

be thought of as a function of gas velocity, the p-w sliding friction coefficient has a slightly greater standardised effect. These findings imply that the responses defining the plug flow behaviour are primarily driven by contact properties, namely p-p sliding and rolling friction and p-w sliding friction coefficients. However, the effect of drag force should not be underestimated from the fluid dynamics perspective as the pressure gradient remains a statistically significant factor for each response parameter.

Considering the four responses (particle exchange rate, plug velocity, plug length, and plug porosity), it can be concluded from this stage of the study that the pressure gradient, p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients, and p-w sliding friction coefficient are the significant parameters for the analysed responses. Therefore, these four parameters will be considered in the next stage of the study together with particle shape. The other four insignificant (or marginally significant, in the case of p-w rolling friction coefficient for the particle exchange rate response) parameters are fixed at their baseline values given in Section 4.1.

4.3. Second stage of simulations

A three-level, five-factor Taguchi experimental design is created in the second stage of the simulations. The same four responses are considered as before.

Fig. 10 shows the main effects and interaction plots for the particle exchange rate. The main effects of pressure gradient, p-p sliding friction coefficient, p-w sliding friction coefficient, and p-p rolling friction coefficient are the same as in Section 4.2, as expected. For the particle shape, the particle exchange rate is higher for the spherical (AR = 1.0) particles, while the values for the oblate and prolate ellipsoids are very similar to each other. As discussed in Section 4.2, this response can be related to the stability of a plug. As spherical particles inherently tend to roll over each other, it makes them less likely to form a stable heap of particles. Therefore, they interact more with the stationary layer, so their particle exchange rates are higher than for the ellipsoidal particles. The interaction plots indicate an interaction between the particle shape and the pressure gradient and p-w sliding friction coefficient.

Fig. 10. Second stage of simulations. Main effects (a) and the interaction plots of particle shape, AR, with the imposed pressure gradient $|\nabla p|$ (b), p-p sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-p} (c), p-w sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-w} (d), and p-p rolling friction coefficient $\mu_{r,p-p}$ (e) for particle exchange rate.

Increasing the pressure gradient by 33.3% decreases the exchange rate by around 17% for the two ellipsoidal particles, whereas this decrease is only around 7% for the spherical particles. This can be attributed to the propensity for non-spherical particles to pack more densely than spherical particles (see Fig. 11). This produces more stable plugs for the non-spherical particles and leads to less particle exchange with the stationary layer. Furthermore, increasing the p-w sliding friction coefficient increases the particle exchange rate by almost 21% for the spherical particles compared to only ~7% for the AR = 0.5 and AR = 2.0 ellipsoidal particles, pointing to the less stable plugs formed by spherical particles.

The variation of the plug porosity with the five factors analysed in this section and their interaction with the particle shape are presented in Fig. 11a and b–e, respectively. In Section 4.2, among the eight factors studied, the p-p rolling and sliding friction coefficients were the most significant factors affecting the plug porosity. Here, it is observed that the particle shape is similarly influential. In general, spherical particles pack less densely than non-spherical particles [23,24]. This holds true for plug flow conveying too, where the porosity of plugs composed of spherical particles is almost 8% larger than for the plugs composed of ellipsoids. This difference has a significant effect in the Ergun equation, leading to a change in the pressure drop of up to 30%, depending on the other parameters in the equation [50]. Furthermore, Fig. 11a indicates that AR = 2.0 (prolate ellipsoid) particles tend to pack more densely than the AR = 0.5 particles, although the difference is relatively small. The interaction plots demonstrate that the particle shape interacts with the p-p and p-w sliding friction coefficient parameters. In Fig. 11c,

we see that as the p-p sliding friction coefficient increases, the effect of particle shape on the plug porosity decreases: the increase of the plug porosity for the spherical particles is less than 2% for $\mu_{p-p} = 0.5$ compared to almost 11% for $\mu_{p-p} = 0.1$. The plug porosity is not affected by the variation of p-w sliding friction coefficient for the AR = 0.5 and AR = 2.0 particles, whereas it decreases as the p-w sliding friction coefficient increases for the AR = 1.0 (spherical) particles.

Fig. 12 illustrates how the plug length is affected by the five factors analysed in the present section and the interaction of the particle shape with the remaining four factors. The main effects plot shows that there is an increase of the plug length as the pressure gradient, p-p sliding friction coefficient, and p-p rolling friction coefficient increase. Conversely, the plug length decreases as the p-w sliding friction coefficient increases (as presented in Section 4.2). The plugs with particles of AR = 0.5 and AR = 2.0 have similar plug lengths which are longer than for the spherical particles. This confirms that the spherical particles are less likely to form stable plugs as they tend to roll over each other unless some rolling friction is introduced to simulate the interlocking of non-spherical particles (also see Fig. 10). Fig. 12c–e demonstrate that the effect of the particle shape depends on the p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients and the p-w sliding friction coefficient. However, it is interesting to note that the nature of this interdependency is different for p-p rolling friction coefficient, for which the effect of particle shape diminishes as it increases, compared to the p-p and p-w sliding friction coefficients which are more affected by particle shape at large values. Sliding friction is known to be a function of contact area between the particles, and a spherical particle has the smallest contact area for a

Fig. 11. Second stage of simulations. Main effects (a) and the interaction plots of particle shape, AR, with the imposed pressure gradient $|\nabla p|$ (b), p-p sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-p} (c), p-w sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-w} (d), and p-p rolling friction coefficient $\mu_{r,p-p}$ (e) for plug porosity.

given volume. It seems that the higher contact area of $AR = 0.5$ and $AR = 2.0$ particles causes higher values of sliding friction coefficients to have a higher impact on plug length.

The main effects and interaction plots for the plug velocity are depicted in Fig. 13. The overall trends from Fig. 7 remain valid. However, since we are now using three levels, we can see how the results vary between the high and low levels. This enables us to observe that increasing p-p sliding friction coefficient from 0.1 to 0.3 increases the plug velocity, but then it remains constant from $\mu_{p-p} = 0.3$ to $\mu_{p-p} = 0.5$. We see a similar behaviour for the p-w sliding friction coefficient, as the plug velocity decreases significantly (from $U_{\text{plug}} \approx 1.7 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ to $U_{\text{plug}} \approx 1.3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) when the p-w sliding friction coefficient is increased from $\mu_{p-w} = 0.24$ to $\mu_{p-w} = 0.26$. However, the decrease is considerably lower when the p-w sliding friction coefficient is further increased. This behaviour is commonly observed in DEM simulations in which systems reach a saturation point friction-wise so further increasing friction does not alter the bulk behaviour [59]. Moreover, the particle shape has a major effect on the plug velocity, where the plug velocity is almost 15% higher for the $AR = 0.5$ and $AR = 2.0$ ellipsoidal particles than for the spherical particles. The smaller porosity of the plugs formed by these particles increases the pressure drop along the plugs, which in turn causes an increase in the plug velocity when the other conditions are kept constant. Also, the smaller particle exchange rate of these particles (see Fig. 10) is another factor facilitating plugs with higher velocities as discussed in Section 4.2. The rolling friction is a DEM parameter that has long been used to mimic the particle shape effect for spherical particles. From Fig. 13e, it is seen that varying the p-p rolling friction

coefficient may diminish the effect of particle shape on plug velocity; almost the same plug velocity is observed for all particle shapes for $\mu_{r,p-p} = 0.2$. This was also valid for the plug length (see Fig. 12) for both p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients. These results imply that these parameters can be used to mimic the steady state behaviour of the non-spherical particles in plug flow conveying by using perfectly spherical particles. This finding is especially important considering the extra computational expense of superquadric particle DEM simulations that can be up to 20–30 times that of their spherical counterparts [60].

5. Conclusions

CFD–DEM simulations have been carried out using ellipsoids to assess the effect of particle shape on plug characteristics in dense phase pneumatic conveying. The interplay between the particle shape, particle size, pressure gradient, and contact parameters have been analysed in a two-stage design of experiments. Four response parameters have been considered: plug velocity, length, porosity, and particle exchange rate. The particle exchange rate is defined as the rate at which particles within the plug are replaced with those in the stationary layer as a percentage per second.

The initial screening process filtered out the factors that exhibited minimal impact on the plug dynamics within the specified parameter intervals, notably the particle size, p-w rolling friction coefficient, and coefficients of restitution. Also, it revealed the pivotal factors, namely the p-w sliding friction coefficient, pressure gradient, and p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients, that significantly affect this phenomenon. The study highlighted:

Fig. 12. Second stage of simulations. Main effects (a) and the interaction plots of particle shape, AR, with the imposed pressure gradient $|\nabla p|$ (b), p-p sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-p} (c), p-w sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-w} (d), and p-p rolling friction coefficient $\mu_{r,p-p}$ (e) for plug length.

- The particle exchange rate is directly proportional to the p-w sliding friction coefficient and inversely proportional to the other three significant parameters.
- Both plug velocity and plug length increase with increasing p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients and pressure gradient, while both decrease with increasing p-w sliding friction coefficient.
- Plug porosity is directly proportional to the p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients.
- The three-level Taguchi design of experiments identified the presence of non-linear variation of response parameters between the levels and the interactions between factors. For example, although plug velocity increases when the p-p sliding friction coefficient is increased from $\mu_{p-p} = 0.1$ to $\mu_{p-p} = 0.3$, it remains constant when μ_{p-p} is further increased from 0.3 to 0.5.
- The spherical particles behave distinctly differently from the non-spherical ones and respond differently to the variation of some factors, e.g., pressure gradient or p-w sliding friction coefficient. This difference is particularly evident when examining plug stability. As a matter of fact, as the pressure gradient increases by 33.3%, the exchange rate decreases by 17% for ellipsoidal particles, in contrast to a decrease of approximately 7% for spherical particles.
- The porosity of the plugs composed of spherical particles is 8% larger than those composed of ellipsoids. Depending on the particle parameters, this 8% increase may cause around a 30% decrease in the pressure drop according to the Ergun equation.
- The parametric analysis has demonstrated that high values of p-p friction and p-p rolling friction tend to reduce the difference in

the response parameters between spherical and non-spherical particles and, in some cases, may result in nearly identical outcomes. For instance, for a high p-p rolling friction coefficient, almost the same plug length is observed for all particle shapes, although the difference between the spherical particle plugs and the ellipsoidal ones is almost 15% at the low value of this factor. The effect of p-p sliding friction coefficient on the plug porosity is another example of this behaviour.

- Increasing certain parameters may induce differences between the responses obtained for different particle shapes, as is seen for the variation of plug length with p-p sliding friction coefficient. At $\mu_{p-p} = 0.1$, the plug length is unaffected by particle aspect ratio. However, at $\mu_{p-p} = 0.5$, the plug length increases around 11% from the spherical to the ellipsoidal particles.
- No considerable differences were observed between the AR = 0.5 and AR = 2.0 ellipsoids.

This is the first robust analysis of the factors affecting plug flow pneumatic conveying of non-spherical particles. Besides analysing the effect of each parameter and their interactions with each other, this comprehensive analysis also gives practical guidance for a practitioner calibrating similar CFD-DEM simulations. In fact, the calibration process can be restricted to three contact parameters without compromising the quality of the simulation predictions. It has also been shown that in CFD-DEM simulations, the p-p sliding and rolling friction coefficients can be used to emulate non-spherical particles by using perfectly spherical particles. However, this does not guarantee that the same dynamics are produced.

Fig. 13. Second stage of simulations. Main effects (a) and the interaction plots of particle shape, AR, with the imposed pressure gradient $|\nabla p|$ (b), p-p sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-p} (c), p-w sliding friction coefficient μ_{p-w} (d), and p-p rolling friction coefficient $\mu_{r,p-p}$ (e) for plug velocity.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Oguzhan Erken: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jin Y. Ooi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Prashant Gupta:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Luigi Capozzi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Kevin J. Hanley:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data are available at the following location:

Base case simulation of 'Parameters affecting plug characteristics in dense phase pneumatic conveying of ellipsoidal particles' (Original data) (Edinburgh DataShare)

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